

DEVELOPMENT OF ENGLISH SPEAKING SKILLS

O'rozboyeva Kumushoy Yaxshimurod qizi

Student, Chirchik State Pedagogical University

orozboyeevakumush6@gmail.com

Tursunboyeva Muhayyoxon Ikrom qizi

Student, Chirchik State Pedagogical University

tursunboyevamuhayyoxon@gmail.com

Abstract: Learning English is one of the most important tasks in modern life, many people are trying to learn English. But there is one thing that everyone has the same difficulty with: getting the pronunciation right. Your grammar and vocabulary are great, but if you cannot pronounce correctly, no one will understand you. This article provides information on how to improve your speaking skills.

Key words: article, speaking skills, English language, development, communication.

INTRODUCTION

This article draws on the principles of teaching and learning foreign languages and on the proceduralization of explicit language knowledge—the process that learners need to go through in order to develop the communicative competence. Communicate more to improve your speaking skills. Language is a means of communication. Therefore, to learn and develop a language, you naturally need to communicate. As for the skill of speaking English quickly, this skill is formed over time with constant practice and more work on yourself. The development of speaking skills consists of different sub-competencies. These sub-skills are pronunciation, grammar and vocabulary. The development of speaking skills depends on the correct use of tasks and exercises given in the lesson.

Any foreign languages training involves the development and development of mandatory skills such as reading, writing and listening. Difficulties is mastering

speaking skills arise for a number of objective and subjective reasons. By objective, we mean the insufficient material and technical equipment of lessons, the inconsistency of the educational and methodological complex with the goals and objectives to be solved in the process of developing speaking skills, the overload of the student collective, which reduces the time of oral communication allotted to the educational and methodological complex for conducting reading classes, the insufficient level of competence of the teacher

As subjective reasons, we consider the student is psychological and emotional state (self-doubt, low self-esteem, fear of making mistakes, etc.); a small amount of knowledge in academic disciplines such as regional studies, cultural studies linguistics; limited vocabulary and inability to use it as Active vocabulary is considered.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODOLOGY

In the last decade, the lexical component of language competence has been given considerable attention in the methodology of teaching foreign languages, which is explained by the reconsideration of the nature of language and the role of

In the scientific theoretical-practical field, which includes issues of English have been collected.

Many researchers consider speaking skill as the main and most important aspect in learning any foreign language, where productive speech activities and oral communication are not possible.

According to some scholars, the ability to speak a foreign languages includes, „students’” motivation, goal orientation, personal interest, speech and thought activity, students interaction within the learning process, contact (emotional, meaningful, personality), situational communication, mastering speech material. The functionality of the process, the content, informativeness and complexity of the educational materials, novelty and expressiveness in the use of verbal and non – verbal means of communication accumulate such indispensable conditions.

And from the point of view of other scientists, speaking is defined as a very multifaceted and complex phenomenon, the mastery of which is primarily the achievement of basic communicative competence.

American scientist Mr. Welles in his work "The orator's guide or rules for speaking and composing" talked about "pronunciation" as one of the important types of speaking skills. He said that pronunciation is called movent, without it our speech will not come out fluently, and the more beautiful our pronunciation is, the more we can attract people around us to our speech.

CONCLUSION

As the main difficulties in teaching English speaking skills and their determining reasons, we identified the following criteria, which represent the theoretical and practical significance of the study:

1) psychological inconvenience. Reasons: lack of confidence in your abilities, fear of making mistakes in front of audience, fear of criticism;

2) lack of thoughts or inability to verbalize them. Reasons: lack of attention, lack of concentration, lack of vocabulary

3) speaking in English or Russian languages. Reasons: lack of active vocabulary on a certain topic in the vocabulary, emotional tension due to an unnatural communication, lack of vocabulary;

4) uneven degree of participation in the speech process and different levels of preparation of students. This is because some students are well prepared and speak English fluently, while others have difficulties, speak little or prefer to „sit back” because they cannot cope with long-term communication in English. As a result, they get less language practice, do not participate in group verbal communication, and lose motivation.

The following criteria can be used to evaluate speaking ability:

- Performing a communicative task;
- Interaction with the interlocutor;
- Lexical-grammatical correctness of speech;
- Keeping the standard of pronunciation (no phonemic errors);

-Intonation correctness of words.

It is clear that the smaller the group, the closer the level of students' preparation and development of speaking skills is to each other, the more productive and successful the learning process will be. As a result of the conducted theoretical research, we note that it is necessary for the teacher not only to have good methodological and technological resources in teaching speaking skills, but also to be able to actively use his psychological and pedagogical knowledge in order to take into account the individual age characteristics of students and the level of their motivation to study.

In conclusion, we should use synonyms, antonyms, words correctly and efficiently in our speech if we follow the above rules and tips. In the development of communication in the classroom, it is necessary to conduct oral tests as often as possible. Vocabulary and grammar do not always need to be checked in writing, rather they should be checked as a conversational task.

References:

1. Galskova, N. D. Theory of learning a foreign language. Language didactics and methods: study guide. Linguistic un-tov and fac. in. spring university ped, study plant/N.D. Galskova, N.L. Gez. Moscow: Izdatelsky center "Akademiya", 2006.-336 p.
2. Салиева З.И. Говорение и его роль в практическом овладении иностранным языком // Проблемы современного образования. 2015 №5
3. Passov, El. Communicative method of teaching foreign language. Prosveshchenie, 1991.-223 p. Moscow:
4. Passov, EL. The basis of methodical training in foreign language. Moscow: Русский язык, 1977.213 p
5. Бирюкова О.А., Саушкина А.И. Метод интервью на уроке английского языка как средство развития навыков говорения (старшая ступень обучения) // Научное обозрение. 2018.- №3.

6. Solovova, E.N. Methodology of teaching foreign languages: basic course lectures: manual for students ped. universities and teachers. 3rd search. Moscow: Prosveshchenie, 2005. 239 p.

7. Frolova N.A., Aleshchanova L.V. Question about methods of formation of foreign language. speaking skills of VPO students // The success of modern natural science. 2014. №11-1.- P. 108-110. [Electronic resource] URL: <https://natural-sciences.ru/ru/article/view?id=34327>

8. Milrud, R.P. Methods of teaching English. English Teaching Methodology: учебное пособие для узов. Moscow: Drofa, 2005.-256 p.

9. Solovyeva. N.A., Pozdnyakova V.R. Mnemonies as an effective way to successfully master a foreign language. Literature and journalism in the intercultural communication of the APR countries of the 20th 21st centuries: materials of the 5th international scientific and practical conference. Khabarovsk, 2021.P. 256-263.